

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article highlights several ways to learn English effectively and some of the modern learning technologies in language learning as well.

Keywords: Language, English, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

INTRODUCTION

By the end of the 20th century, English had finally established itself as a world language. Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, there is a high demand for them to learn the language. Modern foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education in society. People learn such knowledge first at school, college, lyceum, and then at institutes, training courses, or independently by getting acquainted with the basic information sets that help to learn a foreign language.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Teaching and learning English in the research process is popular methods, internet sources were used. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical deductive conclusion, analysis and synthesis, logicity were used.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Language is the main means of communication, without which it is difficult to imagine the existence and development of human society. Today, at a time when there are great changes in social relations in our world, communication media (information technologies) require improving the communicative skills of students. It is important that they exchange ideas in different situations during interaction with other participants of communication, and use language and speech norms correctly. In such conditions, the main purpose of a foreign language is the formation of communicative skills, that is, the implementation of interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language increase is required.

By the end of the 20th century, English had finally established itself as a world language. Its study became compulsory in most schools around the world, and the teaching methodology began to develop by leaps and bounds. Not everyone has the opportunity to attend the courses that led to the emergence of the first method of independent English language learning. Later, many authors tried to independently

create an effective English language learning program, but we will focus on the 4 most popular ones.

1. Schechter's method

This method of learning English is not based on the classical model "from theory to practice", but on the reverse, more natural system of perception. It is very similar to how we learn our mother tongue. The author gives an example of how young children learn how to speak - after all, no one explains to them the rules for building sentences, cases and parts of speech. In the same way, Igor Yuryevich Shekhter suggests learning English.

The essence of the modern method of learning English is that from the first lesson, students are given a certain task, for example, to learn the profession of the interlocutor. In addition, all students play so-called "etudes", where they act in different roles and try to solve a problem. Since communication takes place between people with approximately the same level of knowledge of the language, the fear of using foreign speech, which appears in the communication between the teacher and the student, disappears.

This technique of the English language consists of three stages: in the first, lexical units, words and phrases are given, and only then, in the second and third stages, the use of grammatical and syntactic structures is corrected. The system has repeatedly confirmed its effectiveness, and currently educational psychologists is one of the most successful in terms of.

2. Pimsler method

Dr. Paul Pimsler developed a special system of thirty-minute lessons designed not only for the perception of information, but also for its reproduction. Each lesson is taught by two people: our compatriot and a native English speaker. Thanks to this and special memorization technology each student learns hundreds of English words and phrases for each lesson. The essence of the lesson is to perform the tasks given by the lecturers in sequence.

The undoubted advantages of the technique include its mobility - you can perform audio tasks anywhere: when you are standing in traffic, on your way to work, on the subway on your way to a meeting, or when you are lying in bed before going to bed. The downside is high-quality pronunciation and knowledge acquisition there will be no test.

3. Dragunkin's method

A distinctive feature of Alexander Nikolayevich Dragunkin's system is the focus on the native Russian language when learning any foreign language. The author,

who very boldly called the English language simple, emphasizes that its roots go back to the ancient Russian language, especially the system of grammatical tenses. Dragunkin course students in Russian letters they learn new words that are transcribed, and grammatical constructions are not divided into the 12 tenses known to us from school, but into past, present, future and their changes.

Alexander Nikolaevich has his own network of schools, where you can master three types of courses: basic, short and conversational. For independent study, the book "A Little Leap into English" is offered, which includes a linguist's innovative approach to language learning. Using his system, you can easily understand the use of English verbs, the use of articles you can memorize the rules and easily master the basic principles of sentence construction. Nevertheless, the Dragunkin method has many negative reviews, which criticize the pronunciation and insufficient theoretical knowledge.

4. Petrov method

Dmitry Petrov says that you can learn English in 16 hours. True, the author once again clarifies that we are not talking about language acquisition at the level of a UK-born citizen, but about basic knowledge. His lessons survive the immersion in an English-speaking environment enough to stay, explain your needs and understand the answer.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it should be said that teaching a modern language is aimed at forming a more cultured person, who has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. For sure, teachers are the most they can learn about advanced approaches and then integrate them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations use multimedia capabilities to send and receive information is moving to a new level using The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the entire educational process.

Speech skills in trainings during the educational process adequate attention should be paid to formation and development of social flexibility. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct organization of the training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then students can think independently they receive, their will is trained.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdulakim o'g'li, A. I. (2022). INGLIZ TILIDA GAP STRUKTURASINING TIZIMLINISHIDA YORDAMCHI SO 'Z TURKUMLARINING ROLI. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal, 1(3), 137-140.
2. Abdilkadimovna, K. N. (2022). THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF GENDER RELATED WORDS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE. YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS,1(2),179-182.
3. Abdisheribov, S., Yo'Ldosheva, M., & Jumayeva, M. (2022). IMPLEMENTING CREATIVE WRITING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING CLASSROOMS. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1343-1347.
4. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. – London., 2001.
5. Johnson, K. E. The Sociocultural Turn and Its Challenges for Second Language Teacher Education. // TESOL Quarterly., – London., 2006.
6. Kovecses, Zoltan. Metaphors of Anger, Pride, and Love: A Lexical Approach to the Structure of Concepts. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamin's Publishing Company.
7. Kamiljanovna, Z. D., O'G'Li, A. S. J., & Jumayeva, M. B. (2022). THE ANALYSIS OF HIGHER ORDER THINKING SKILLS. Science and innovation, 1(Special Issue 2), 672-676.
8. Ravshanovna, G. N. (2022, April). THE STUDY OF THE MEANING OF THE WORD TOLERANCE IN OTHER LANGUAGES. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-9).
9. Ravshanovna, G. N., & Anvarovna, Y. D. (2022, May). INGLIZ VA OZBEK TILLARIDAGI TURIZMDAGI ATAMALARNING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK JIHATLARI. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 14-17).
10. Пассов Э. И. Общительный метод обучения иностранного разговора. – Москва., 1985.

